

Enhancing public transport systems through scalable real-time forecasting solutions for the case study of Rennes*

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Abstract—A reliable public transport system is critical in promoting its preference over private vehicles, subsequently leading to a reduction in CO2 emissions and air pollution. A public transport forecasting model enhances travel schedule efficiency, trip planning and therefore service reliability. Due to the large volume of trajectory data and high computational demands, developing scalable forecasting solutions is valuable. In the context of the TANGENT H2020 project, data-driven methodologies are developed for real-time supply prediction problems. This paper focuses on forecasting solutions for the public transport system for the case study of Rennes. It presents a pipeline for bus travel time prediction which is both accurate and computationally efficient, and which can deal with missing trajectories by defining square grids and a state-of-the-art forecasting model. The results show that as the grid size is incrementally increased, improvements in predictive accuracy are observed up to an optimal point where the accuracy goes beyond state-of-the-art.

I. INTRODUCTION

The increasing demand for sustainable urban mobility increases the necessity of a reliable public transport system. This paper aims to predict public transportation travel time, as one of the key measurements of traffic supply to assess the transportation infrastructure. Short-term predictions are useful for public transportation systems due to several reasons. It enables real-time monitoring and management of public transport operations, since operators can identify and respond to disruptions by dynamically adjusting schedules, rerouting vehicles, etc. Furthermore, short-term predictions help passengers plan their journeys more effectively by providing accurate information about arrival times and potential delays. This information should lead to increased passenger satisfaction, proactive communication with passengers, and therefore improved service reliability.

Data-driven approaches capture features in traffic data and use them to predict the future traffic state. With the advancement of deep learning models in various fields [1], researchers have developed multiple models for traffic supply forecasting, which surpassed traditional methods (e.g., statistical methods) in performance. One of the early models

DCRNN (Diffusion Convolutional Recurrent Neural Network) [2], presents a novel forecasting approach by integrating graph convolutional and recurrent neural networks which improved the state-of-the-art significantly. Meanwhile, other models are developed and improved the DCRNN model by introducing many different components like an attention mechanism for spatial and temporal aspects of the time series data [3], [4]. MTGNN (Multivariate Time Series Forecasting with Graph Neural Networks) [5] is one of the open-source state-of-the-art models that perform best in many datasets.

This work focuses on bus trajectory travel time predictions for the city of Rennes, one of the case studies within the TANGENT H2020 project. Buses are an important component of public transportation systems by connecting different modes of transport, improving collective efficacy. To the best of our knowledge, MTGNN has not yet been applied to bus trajectory travel time predictions.

A review of bus travel time predictions is given by [6]. They identified that in most studies, one or two-step predictions were performed. Each step is usually 5 to 15 minutes. Hence the research should move towards longer prediction horizons to allow for a more comprehensive approach to improve the bus services by allowing the users to plan their journeys longer before their departure. [7] utilizes tensor decomposition and graph embeddings for short-term trajectory travel time prediction. In another work, [8] uses Long short-term memory (LSTM) for predictions of up to four time steps in the future. The proposed work in our paper increases the prediction horizon up to eight steps. Furthermore, we aim to predict the travel times of each route at a city-wide level. Most of the research focuses on specific segments of public transport, like link-based or stop-based methodologies [6], [9]. The proposed methodology goes beyond predicting each route in the dataset since it can predict the travel time in any origin-destination pair in the study area, making it suitable for planning new bus routes as well. The dataset of Rennes contains an extreme amount of missing values, while most prediction models in literature use complete data [9].

In summary, this paper considers the prediction of travel times on public transport routes at a city-wide level up to eight time steps which is defined as up to 2 hours from the start of the journey until the end of the journey which is on average around 50 minutes. This study uses sparse data from a real-world dataset in the city of Rennes.

*This work has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 955273 (TANGENT).

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II. METHODOLOGY

The process of predicting bus travel times involves several steps. This work is based on trajectory data, which is generated from GPS sensors. The main challenge with trajectory data is samples where trajectories are missing or lack an identification for each distinct journey. Therefore, the first step, data preprocessing, is crucial as it ensures a more precise representation of the road network and allows for the identification of individual journeys. Trajectories can be either represented by map matching or grid-based algorithms. [7] has a section comparing two methodologies where they preferred grid-based algorithms due to scalability, processing speed, and coverage. Once the trajectories are represented, the forecasting is conducted in the next step, followed by the utilization of these forecasts for route travel time predictions in the fourth step. Finally, the predictions are evaluated by comparing them with the ground truths. These steps are outlined below.

A. Trajectory preprocessing

The methodology starts with a preprocessing step. First, some general checks are performed: remove duplicates and out-of-service buses. Next, each journey is identified as follows. Each line ID can have a different destination and direction. These are distinguished by allocating a route ID. Multiple buses run in one route, therefore a bus ID is added to the route ID. Afterward, each journey is identified by calculating continuity in corresponding trajectories during the day. Another crucial preprocessing step is denoising due to e.g. obstructions with the GPS signals.

B. Make a grid based on the observed boundaries

To make trajectory datasets applicable to the model, a grid-based approach [7] is performed in this step. Square regions are defined with a length that is almost around "grid size". The regions without any passing trajectories are removed, and the remaining regions are represented as R-trees [10] for faster spatial access. R-tree organizes data in a tree-like structure where each node represents a bounding rectangle which makes it easier to work with spatial data like trajectories. When a new trajectory is added to the tree, the algorithm traverses the tree from the root node and chooses a path that requires the least number of enlargements of the corresponding bounding rectangles until it reaches a leaf node. Then the grid is added. To assign a trajectory to a grid, the tree is traversed from the root node and only child nodes are explored if their bounding rectangles intersect with the search query. Using R-trees instead of linear searching significantly reduces the search time in large datasets. In the next step, each trajectory is assigned to its respective grid. The journey time is determined by calculating the difference between the first and the last time the bus was detected in the grid. Furthermore, the average speed of each grid is calculated by averaging over bus speeds. The journey time and speed are resampled to 15-minute intervals to reduce noise and make the data consistent and comparable.

C. Forecasting the journey time on these grids

In the next step, a spatiotemporal forecasting model is trained on the processed data. MTGNN is used as a state-of-the-art forecasting model. It has three main components: a graph learning layer, a graph convolution module, and a temporal convolution module. MTGNN's graph learning layer automatically learns the underlying graph structure using a data-driven approach directly from time series data to give more weight to the former case and less weight to the latter case. Then the travel time predictions in grids are used for route travel time predictions. Its ability to start without a graph or update the original graph makes it very interesting in the traffic forecasting context as the road network can be made with different methods such as the shortest paths between each pair of nodes or the free flow travel time between each of them. Hence, in many models, every node affects its closest neighboring nodes. However, it may not be the case for many road networks where a farther node in a highway has more effect than a nearby secondary road. One advantage is its data-driven ability to improve the adjacency matrix. This is very useful since the definition of the adjacency matrix is not clear. The starting adjacency matrix is defined using the midpoint of each grid and their Haversine distance to other grids.

The Haversine formula is widely used to estimate the great-circle distance between two points on the surface of a sphere, given their longitudes and latitudes.

Let ϕ_1, λ_1 and ϕ_2, λ_2 be the geographical latitude and longitude of two points on the Earth's surface, respectively, and let r denote the Earth's radius. The Haversine formula is given by:

$$d = 2r \arcsin \left(\sqrt{\sin^2 \left(\frac{\Delta\phi}{2} \right) + \cos(\phi_1) \cos(\phi_2) \sin^2 \left(\frac{\Delta\lambda}{2} \right)} \right)$$

where:

$$\Delta\phi = \phi_2 - \phi_1$$

$$\Delta\lambda = \lambda_2 - \lambda_1$$

In this study we only need grid travel times. However, the input to the model is both average speed and travel time to increase its accuracy. The model is trained using masked mean absolute error (MAE) loss, which is useful when missing values are present in the dataset. MAE, calculated in minutes, is the average of the absolute differences between the predictions and ground truths. The masking ignores the model's output when the ground truth is missing which causes the model to not get any gradients from those timestamps. The trained model learns to use the inherent biases and neighboring grid information on timestamps that historical data is unavailable, making it robust to missing values.

To calculate Masked MAE [2], Let $preds$ and $labels$ be tensors of the same shape and n be the number of timestamps in a prediction window. We define the mask M as follows:

$$M_i = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } preds_i \neq \text{null} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Normalize the mask to have mean 1:

$$M \leftarrow \frac{M}{\text{mean}(M)}$$

Calculate the absolute error:

$$L = |preds - labels|$$

Apply the mask:

$$L = L \cdot M$$

Return the mean of the masked loss:

$$\text{mean}(L) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n L_i$$

D. Calculate the bus journey time using the grid journey times

We begin by identifying all the grid segments that a bus traverses from its origin to its destination. The travel time predictions for each of these grid segments are then aggregated to form the overall predicted travel time for the entire route.

Our methodology has even the capability to predict travel times for routes that are currently not served by any bus. This is achieved by considering each pair of segments that could potentially form a new bus route. The model uses historical data from other routes within the same grid to estimate the travel times. This capability enables planning and analysis for potential future route expansions which can be accommodated with simulation models to develop a dynamic framework to evaluate how expansions in service can impact overall demand. This framework can help create efficient schedules to match demand peaks.

E. Comparison with ground truths

To evaluate the performance on a test dataset, MAE, Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE), and Root mean squared error metrics (RMSE) are calculated. MAPE expresses these errors as percentages, which is useful for comparison when the travel time differs significantly between different routes. RMSE, on the other hand, calculates the square root of the average of squared differences which emphasizes larger errors more significantly compared to MAE. It is useful to evaluate the model's performance for the prediction of more complex patterns like anomalies. The model generates the predictions at 15-minute intervals. However, actual bus journeys occur at varying times, dictated by network conditions and their respective schedules. To align the model's predictions with recorded real-world data, we match each prediction to the closest recorded time in the ground truth data.

TABLE I: Percentage of missing values for each grid size

Grid Size	Missing Values
125×125	95.426%
250×250	92.618%
500×500	89.473%
1000×1000	85.935%
1500×1500	83.072%
2000×2000	82.766%
2500×2500	80.001%

The ground truth data is calculated by tracking the trajectories of individual buses from their origin bus station to the destination station. For each journey, the ground truth timestamp corresponds to the moment the bus begins its movement from origin to destination. The timestamp where the bus starts its movement is considered the timestamp for the journey. The duration of the journey is then calculated by subtracting the initial timestamp from the timestamp recorded when the bus arrives at the destination station. Incomplete journeys are omitted from the comparison.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Rennes case study is one of the TANGENT project case studies, which is used to apply the proposed methodology. The dataset consists of 2,409,223 trajectories that span from 2023-06-08 05:26:00 to 2023-11-05 21:59:00, representing 12 routes.

Fig. 1 depicts the trajectory for line ID 11, direction 0 to the destination of Roazhon Park. The bus route starts at the blue point and ends at the yellow endpoint. The colors in between, represent the minutes from the start point, as shown in the legend on the right-hand side of the figure. One of the main issues with calculating journey times from trajectories is the problem of data quality, as shown by the peak in green (Fig. 1b). This trajectory travels impossible distances in a short amount of time. These can be caused by not having a clear sky view or other obstructions for GPS signals. Therefore, the trajectories with speeds higher than 80 km/h are removed (Fig. 1c).

After data preprocessing, a grid is constructed. This is depicted in Fig. 2, where Rennes and its surroundings, are divided into grids of 2500 by 2500 meters. The boundaries have been determined based on the historical trajectories.

The number of bus trajectories is limited compared to the number that can be obtained from private vehicles using navigation apps. To make the best use of the available data, we average the travel time and speed over 15-minute intervals, as explained in the methodology section. Consequently, the dataset has a large number of missing values at these intervals. Such sparsity makes the data imputation harder for the model, specifically for smaller grid sizes, which affects the forecasting performance. The following table shows the percentage of missing values in the dataset.

In the next step, MTGNN is applied to the grid. The effect of different grid sizes is investigated. To evaluate the performance of the methodology, the following error metrics are used: MAE, MAPE, and RMSE.

(a) Trajectory for the bus route from start (blue) to end location (yellow).

(b) As can be seen by the extreme fluctuation the raw data needs to be cleaned.

(c) The peak is removed by removing high velocities.

Fig. 1: Illustration of trajectory data cleaning process.

Fig. 2: Rennes and its surroundings divided in grids of size 2500 by 2500 meters

The impact of the grid size on accuracy is depicted in Fig. 3. It shows RMSE, MAE, and MAPE as a mean metric over all the routes. It demonstrates that the grid size of 1000 yields the highest accuracy. There is a sharp increase in accuracy when transitioning from a grid size of 125 to 250. This improvement indicates that a grid size of 125 is not suitable for the trajectory sampling rate of 1 minute.

The results show that different grid sizes have different impacts on forecasting accuracy. Where very small and very large sizes have lower accuracy compared to grid sizes in the middle. The problem for small grid sizes is caused by the fact that the sampling rate is 1 minute. Furthermore, a small grid size means that some trajectories may pass the grid without being detected or only be detected once, which isn't enough since the grid journey times are calculated using the first and the latest detection of a trajectory. On the other hand, for very large grids, some streets may overlap, and the journey time is going to be the average journey time of several routes. This effect is smaller than missed detections.

The error metrics are listed in Table II for the different routes at the prediction horizon of 2 hours (8 time steps) with a grid size of 1000 by 1000 meters. The MEAN row gives an aggregate view of the average performance of the model

Fig. 3: Illustration of trajectory data cleaning process.

for all routes, while the STD row measures the variability of these errors across these routes.

An MAE of 4.466 minutes and MAPE of 9.394% over 12 routes demonstrates the effectiveness of the model in predicting bus travel times, even two hours in advance. Although a direct comparison with other studies is not feasible due to the use of different and proprietary datasets and models that most studies use, we can get an insight into performance by comparing MAPE. For example, In another similar research, [11] reports a MAPE of 15.29% where the

TABLE II: Comprehensive Performance Metrics by Route ID

Route ID (Line-Direction-Destination)	MAE (Minutes)	MAPE (%)	RMSE	Average Travel Time (Minutes)
11-0-Roazhon Park	4.572	9.662	5.502	47.3
11-1-République	4.678	19.277	5.792	24.3
11-1-Saint-Saëns	5.863	12.620	7.214	46.4
54-0-Le Rheu	6.243	11.05	9.306	56.5
54-0-Le Rheu/Cintré	4.204	8.180	5.281	51.4
54-0-Le Rheu/Chavagne	4.539	7.994	5.510	56.8
54-0-Mordelles	3.345	7.205	4.175	46.4
55-0-Mordelles	2.748	6.068	3.473	45.3
55-0-Chavagne	4.502	7.888	5.303	57.1
55-0-Mordelles Le Verger	5.103	7.952	6.447	64.2
56-0-Chavagne	3.485	6.678	4.122	52.2
56-1-Rennes	4.311	8.143	5.280	52.9
MEAN	4.466	9.394	5.617	50
STD	0.950	3.458	1.476	9.4

average travel time is less than 8 minutes. [9] also deals with significant missing values. They report an average MAPE of 9.85% over 3 routes. We can also compare our accuracy with studies that predict taxi travel times, [7] reported MAPEs of 12.32% and 12.99% for Beijing and Shanghai, respectively. Additionally, [8] reported a MAPE of 13% for one of their studied routes in Toronto. In summary, our proposed method improves the MAPE for 2-3% compared to the state-of-the-art.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This paper outlines a pipeline for bus travel time prediction in the city of Rennes which is both accurate and computationally efficient, and which can deal with missing trajectories. It's based on bus trajectories which are sampled minutely as the input to the procedure. The area is divided into square grids with predefined sizes, in which the average travel time and speed are calculated. These average speeds and travel times are then fed as input to the MTGNN model. The model forecasts the future travel time for each grid and finally, these predictions are aggregated to estimate the future travel times for each bus route. We achieved a mean absolute error of 4.466 minutes over 12 routes that take over 50 minutes on average, which demonstrates the effectiveness of the model in predicting travel times two hours in advance from the start of the journey. A key finding of this study is the influence of the grid size on accuracy, where both exceedingly small and large grid sizes reduced accuracy. The methodology and results of this study can be utilized to enhance the reliability and efficiency of bus services and user planning of public transportation usage. It should be noted that the proposed pipeline can predict the travel time in any origin-destination pair in the study area, making it suitable for planning new bus routes.

V. FUTURE WORK

In this section, we propose three possible avenues to improve the proposed methodology.

A. Expanding simulation coverage with Kriging models

The proposed methodology in this study demonstrates the ability to simulate the introduction of new bus routes between

each pair of grids in the study area. This allows using it in the planning of new bus routes. As future work, we propose using Kriging models [12], [13] to estimate travel times in areas without any historical data. By incorporating geospatial interpolation techniques, the simulation's scope could expand beyond the area of study, therefore allowing for route planning in other areas of interest.

B. Advancing spatial representation with non-homogeneous shapes

The current methodology employs square grids as the foundational spatial unit for route simulation. To more accurately reflect the complexities of urban structure, future work can adopt non-homogeneous and irregular shapes derived from the analysis of bus routes and trajectories optimizing entry and exit points in each section.

C. Data fusion with other transport modes

In the proposed methodology, several steps were taken to address the issue of data sparsity within the dataset. These strategies include the application of masked losses in the deep learning model, trajectory assignment to spatial grids, and temporal aggregation. Despite these steps, the accuracy of our model may be further improved by integrating trajectories from different traffic modes with the data obtained from sources like navigation applications. Although the transport mode is different here, this supplementary data may offer correlations to public transport modes, improving the accuracy of the forecasting models. Additionally, incorporating external features such as weather conditions, holiday calendars, and such can further improve the accuracy of the models.

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